

Exploring the Effect of Parental Pressure and Gender in Shaping Educational Adjustment in School Students

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Abstract

The present study aims to explore the Effect of Parental Pressure and Gender in Shaping Educational Adjustment in high school students. For this purpose 'Parental Pressure Scale made by Suman Kumari and Rama Maikhuri and Educational Adjustment Inventory made by Seema Rani and Basant Bahadur Singh, was administered on 80 male and 80 female students of Durg District. Descriptive (mean and standard deviation) and inferential (2×2 ANOVA) statistical techniques were used to analyze the data. The results showed that parental pressure has a significant effect on the educational adjustment of students. However, there is no significant effect of gender on educational adjustment. A significant interaction effect between parental pressure and gender was found, suggesting that the influence of parental pressure on adjustment varies by gender. Specifically, boys under high parental pressure are more maladjusted compared to girls in similar conditions. Conversely, boys under low parental pressure exhibit better educational adjustment than girls.

Keywords

Parental Pressure , Educational Adjustment, Academic environment, School Student.

Introduction

In recent years, educators, clinical psychologists, and psychiatrists have voiced strong criticism of the excessive burden placed on young students by the Indian educational system. Media reports—especially in newspapers and magazines—have repeatedly highlighted the rising incidence of learning and behavioral issues among students, linking them to intense academic pressure. This pressure is largely the result of a rigid curriculum and the high expectations imposed by both teachers and parents.

Numerous case studies across India reveal how this academic strain has led to serious psychological consequences for students, including psychosomatic disorders, depression, and, in extreme cases, running away from home or suicide.

For Indian students, academic pressure arises from four primary and interconnected sources: curriculum-related, school-related, parental, and internal pressures. The current curriculum is predominantly exam-oriented, which fosters rote learning and unhealthy competition, rather than encouraging critical thinking and creativity. In addition, schools often fail to accommodate individual learning differences, instead promoting uniformity and conformity. This approach limits students' freedom to express themselves and discourages independent thought, placing further strain on their development. Parental pressure also plays a significant role, as parents frequently set unrealistic academic expectations, driven by their aspirations for social mobility and professional success. As a result, children often internalize these external demands, creating a form of self-imposed stress and anxiety. This internal pressure, compounded by the others, can be particularly detrimental to a student's mental and emotional well-being. Although a few alternative schools attempt to shift away from this "10% marks race" by adopting more holistic and student-centered educational practices, such institutions are still rare in the broader Indian educational landscape.

Objective of study

The objectives of the study are given below:

To find out the effect of Parental Pressure and Gender on the Educational Adjustment of high school students.

Review of Literature

Qadeer, Anwar, & Khan (2025) have conducted a study on parental pressure and its impacts on students' mental health. This study explores how parental over-expectations affect students psychologically, cognitively, behaviorally, and relationally. Increased pressure from parents is linked to higher levels of anxiety, depression, low self-esteem, and emotional withdrawal. Cultural and socioeconomic factors shape how this pressure is experienced—seen as supportive in collectivist cultures but overbearing in individualistic ones. Wealthier families may exert more academic pressure due to greater resources, while lower-income families may prioritize immediate financial returns. Strained parent-child relationships during such times can lead to emotional detachment or resistance.

Singh & Singh (2024) have studied the relationship between school adjustment and study habits among senior secondary students. Findings reveal that there is no significant

relationship between school adjustment and study habits among government senior secondary students. Whereas among private senior secondary students, there is a positive correlation between study habits and school adjustment.

Rajput and Bala (2023) conducted a study to explore the educational adjustment of secondary school students in Sonipat. The research aimed to examine educational adjustment concerning gender and type of school. The results, based on the norms of the Educational Adjustment Inventory manual, indicated that secondary school students exhibited an above-average level of educational adjustment. Furthermore, it was observed that girl students demonstrated significantly higher educational adjustment than boy students. However, there was no significant difference in educational adjustment between students from private and government schools in Sonipat. Interestingly, while educational adjustment did not vary significantly by school type, academic achievement was found to be higher among girl students and those attending private schools, compared to male students and those enrolled in government schools. The study also revealed a significant and positive correlation between educational adjustment and academic achievement among secondary school students, suggesting that better-adjusted students tend to perform better academically.

Dilek Gençtanırım Kurti (2022)) conducted a study on Effect of Family, Friends and School Climate on School Adjustment of Middle School Students , The results of the study revealed that school climate, academic grade, gender, family support and peer relationships have significant direct effects in explaining the school adjustment of middle school students. Additionally, the gender and family relationships variables mediated by school climate, and the peer relationships variable mediated by academic grade, had significant effects on school adjustment.

Pramila and Shakuntala (2022) investigated the impact of peer pressure, parental pressure & school environment on academic cheating. In this study, peer pressure (High & Low), parental pressure (High & Low) and school environment (Good & Poor) has been treated as independent variables whereas academic cheating has been treated as dependent variable. Method of current study was descriptive survey. The 3-way ANOVA with 2×2×2 factorial design was employed to analyse the data. A significant main effect of peer pressure, parental pressure & school environment on academic cheating among Sr. Sec. school students was found. Interaction effect of peer pressure, parental pressure & school environment on academic cheating among Sr. Sec. school students was also found to be significant.

Ali, et. al. (2021) conducted a study on "Does Parental Pressure for High Marks Effects Negatively the Secondary Schools Students in Pakistan?" In Pakistan, most of the parents of school-going children are not literate. This investigation assessed the association among "parental stress for high marks," "examination phobia", "students' suicide intention," & dropout rates of pupils in sec. school of Pakistan. Parental pressure & students' suicide intent was highly correlated. It was also found that there exists a significant relation in between parental stress for higher grades & learner's dropout . Furthermore, a association was also showed among the "parents 'stress for high marks," "students' dropout," & "suicide intention," & "examination phobia."

Niaz, Mujahid and Atta (2021) investigated the degrees of parental pressure for high English marks at the secondary level in the Mardan district. The results revealed that parents put a lot of pressure on their children to do well in English, but the kids struggle to meet the goals. The pupils' emotional and psychological issues caused by this occurrence cause them to leave school. The research recommended that principals should tell parents of the negative impacts of their pressure on pupils through PTC (Parents' Teachers' Council) meetings in order to improve the students' grades in English and increase their competence.

Allison (2020) studied how parental pressure affected athletes' stress levels, sense of self, and general well-being. According to the findings, parental pressure to excel has a detrimental impact, but kids' push to excel has a more beneficial impact. The research shows that, in the end, how the athlete interprets these actions has the most impact on their athletic career, even if a parent may think they are talking and doing in the proper ways.

Main Text

Parental pressure is particularly significant in the Indian context. Unlike their Western counterparts, Indian parents across socio-economic backgrounds view education as a key instrument of social mobility and modernization. The ambition for children to pursue prestigious careers—especially in engineering, medicine, or other high-status professions—leads many parents to place unrealistic expectations on their children.

The term "parental pressurisation" refers to a combination of beliefs, expectations, behaviors, and dispositions that cause psychological and sometimes physical strain on children. These may manifest through: Over-anxious or overly ambitious attitudes. Controlling and rigid parenting styles . Excessive academic demands beyond a child's capacity. Learning, under such circumstances, becomes a structured and externally controlled activity, often robbing children of autonomy and intrinsic motivation. Even leisure-time activities such as hobbies, television, or extracurricular pursuits tend to be heavily scheduled and monitored. In dual-income households, where both parents work, children's lives may run on tight routines, leaving little room for spontaneous or independent activity. Such constant programming of children's daily routines can lower their perceived autonomy and sense of competence—both essential for healthy motivation and adjustment during adolescence. Parents, being the primary caregivers and authority figures in a child's life, significantly influence the child's emotional well-being and adjustment.

Need of Study- Given the deeply rooted cultural and systemic dimensions of parental pressure in India, there is an urgent need to study this phenomenon more systematically. Such research is essential not only for understanding its impact on the mental health and educational adjustment of children, but also for informing more balanced educational practices and parenting approaches in a rapidly changing society. That's why researchers choose this topic and the title of the Research is **“Exploring the Effect of Parental Pressure and Gender in Shaping Educational Adjustment in School Students.”**

Sampling

In the present study, the researcher employed the method of random sampling. Each individual in the population had an equal and independent chance of being selected for the sample. A total of 160 students from the 9th grade were selected, comprising 80 boys and 80 girls.

Tools Used

- In the present study, the following tools were used for data collection:
1. Parental Pressure Scale (PPS–KSMR) by Suman Kumari and Rama Maikhuri.
 2. Educational Adjustment Inventory (EAI–RSSBB) made by Seema Rani and Basant Bahadur Singh.

Analysis

H_{1,0} There exists no significant main and interactional effect of Parental Pressure and Gender on the Educational Adjustment of High School Students. The Data collected concerning this hypothesis was evaluated using a 2x2 FACTORIAL DESIGN ANOVA. Table 1 summarizes the findings of this investigation:

Table- 01
Summary of 2x2 FACTORIAL DESIGN ANOVA for effect of Parental Pressure and Gender on the Educational Adjustment of students.

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Parental Pressure	2451.953	1	2451.953	21.26**
Gender	3.287	1	3.287	.029 ^{NS}
Parental Pressure X Gender	490.646	1	490.646	4.26*
Error (With in)	15337.927	133	115.323	
Total	193463.000	137		

*= 0.05 Significance Level, **= 0.01 Significance Level, NS= Not Significant

Main Effects of Parental Pressure

Table 01 shows that the F value of 21.26 (df 1/133) was found to be significant for Parental Pressure. This indicates that the two means are statistically different. Thus, the proposed hypothesis “There exists no significant effect of Parental Pressure on Educational Adjustment of students”, is not accepted. So it is inferred that there exists a significant effect of Parental Pressure on Educational Adjustment of students.

Table – 02
Mean of Educational Adjustment among students belonging to High parental pressure and low parental pressure

Parental Pressure	Mean	SD	N
High	40.00	08.53	70
Low	31.29	12.79	67

Table No 2 indicates that the mean value of educational adjustment for students experiencing high parental pressure and low parental pressure is 40.00 and 31.29, respectively. Since lower scores on the educational adjustment scale indicate better adjustment, this result suggests that students subjected to lower parental pressure demonstrate significantly higher educational adjustment compared to their peers under high parental pressure. The observed difference in mean scores indicates a notable impact of parental pressure on students' educational adjustment. Specifically, as parental pressure decreases, students tend to adjust better educationally, highlighting the potential negative effect of excessive parental demands on school adaptation and performance.

Gender

Table 01 shows that the F value of 0.029 for df 1/133 was found to be insignificant for the Gender difference. This indicates that the two means are not statistically different. Thus, the proposed hypothesis “There exists no significant effect of gender on Educational Adjustment of students”, is accepted. So it is inferred that there exists no significant effect of gender on Educational Adjustment of students.

Interaction Effect of Parental Pressure and Gender

Table No. 1 shows that the obtained F value 4.26 (df 1/133) for interaction between

Parental Pressure and Gender was found to be significant at 0.05 level. This indicates that there is a significant interaction effect between Parental Pressure and Gender on the Educational Adjustment of students. Therefore, the null hypothesis— “There exists no significant effect of interaction between Parental Pressure and Gender on Educational Adjustment of students.” is not accepted. So it is inferred that there is a significant interactional effect of Parental Pressure and Gender on Educational Adjustment of students.

Table - 03
Mean of Educational Adjustment of students with respect to Parental Pressure and Gender

Parental Pressure / Gender	Boys			Girls		
	Mean	SD	N	Mean	SD	N
High Parental Pressure	41.74	09.06	35	38.26	7.72	35
Low Parental Pressure	29.45	12.74	37	33.56	12.69	30

Table No – 03 shows that the mean value of educational adjustment is high in boys , who belon Table No. 03 shows that the mean value of educational adjustment is higher in boys under high parental pressure compared to girls under the same condition. Since higher mean values indicate greater maladjustment, this suggests that boys experiencing high parental pressure are more maladjusted than girls in similar circumstances. On the other hand, boys under low parental pressure show better educational adjustment (i.e., lower mean scores) compared to girls with low parental pressure. This indicates that boys benefit more, in terms of adjustment, from lower parental pressure than girls do. This finding suggests that the influence of parental pressure on educational adjustment varies by gender. Specifically, boys experiencing high parental pressure tend to be maladjusted, whereas under conditions of low parental pressure, their educational adjustment improves.

Findings

The study revealed that their parents' pressure influenced the educational adjustment of students. Students under high parental pressure experienced poorer educational adjustment, while those under low parental pressure showed better academic adjustment. There was no gender disparity between boys and girls in educational adjustment. There are several social and psychological reasons for the similarities observed in the educational adjustment of boys and girls.

Conclusion

The findings indicate that students' educational adjustment is significantly influenced by parental pressure . However, excessive parental pressure was associated with poorer adjustment outcomes. Students with high parental pressure often experience increased stress, anxiety, and fear of failure, which can negatively impact their educational adjustment. When parents place excessive expectations on their children, it may lead to a high-pressure environment where students feel overwhelmed rather than supported. This can result in decreased motivation, difficulty concentrating, and lower self-confidence, all of which hinder their ability to adjust effectively to academic demands. On the other hand, students with low parental pressure tend to have more autonomy and emotional freedom, allowing them to develop self-motivation, better time management, and a healthier attitude toward learning. Supportive rather than controlling parenting encourages open communication and emotional security, which fosters better educational adjustment. Notably, no significant gender differences were observed in educational adjustment, which can be attributed to a range of social and psychological factors. The increasing emphasis on gender equality and inclusive educational practices has led to more equitable support systems within both families and schools. Equal encouragement for boys and girls to engage in extracurricular activities and social interactions has fostered similar levels of adaptability within the school environment. Moreover, consistent school policies, access to counselling services, and student-centred teaching approaches have helped meet the diverse needs of students irrespective of gender. Consequently, both boys and girls are comparably equipped to manage academic demands, peer relationships, and institutional expectations, resulting in negligible gender disparities in educational adjustment.

Suggestions for the future Study

- The following recommendations were made based on the findings of the study:
1. Promote Healthy Parental Involvement- Encourage parents to support their children without placing unrealistic expectations or excessive pressure on academic performance.
 2. Provide Counselling Services- Schools should offer regular counselling to help students manage stress, build coping skills, and express their concerns.
 3. Enhance Communication Between Parents and Teachers
Regular parent-teacher interactions can help align expectations and ensure parents understand their child’s abilities and needs.
1. Encourage Emotional Support at Home- Parents should create an emotionally safe environment where children feel valued regardless of their academic outcomes.
 2. Promote Extracurricular Participation- Involvement in sports, arts, or hobbies can provide a healthy outlet for stress and help students build confidence.

3. Develop a Supportive School Environment- Teachers should use student-centred teaching methods and show understanding toward individual learning differences.

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